

Dynamic monitoring of construction site activities based on BIM

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Abstract

The efficient quantification of construction project progress is vital for effective project management, necessitating a balance between computation time and accuracy in quantification methods. Real-time information on completed work quantities is essential for timely decision-making by project managers. Existing vision-based approaches for automated progress quantification have faced implementation challenges such as computational complexity, specialized personnel, and expensive equipment. In response, this study introduces easily implementable pipelines that comprehensively quantify building progress, including element progress tracking and element analysis. Two methods are presented in this paper. The first method compares the number of points in the as-built model with those anticipated from the as-designed model of the same point intensities. It seamlessly integrates the as-designed BIM model with scan data using the user-friendly visual programming tool, Grasshopper3D, streamlining progress quantification with minimal user input for basic data alignment. The second method transfers the as-built point cloud to the mesh and compares it with the as-design model, the as-design model was populated with points, and progress can be obtained by calculating the number of points on the mesh. The second method significantly reduces computation requirements for the entire process and increases analysis speed by more than a hundred times.

Furthermore, the potential of automated construction progress monitoring through the integration of as-planned BIM and as-built point cloud data is substantial, offering opportunities for expediting construction work and detecting discrepancies. In Chapter 2, this paper introduces an automatic approach to the analysis elements based on the point cloud, and to generate point cloud sections automatically with the function of integration with other sources of data.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/UBqGeSp-sy8>

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